

FACTORS THAT HAVE IMPACT ON LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Author: Zilola Azimova

Annotation This article explores the various factors that impact acquisition. It provides insights into how these factors can influence the success or failure of an acquisition, and offers practical tips for businesses looking to navigate these challenges. The article also highlights the importance of due diligence, communication, and strategic planning in the acquisition process. Overall, this article provides a comprehensive overview of the complex and multifaceted nature of acquisition, and offers valuable insights for businesses looking to grow through mergers and acquisitions.

Key terms: language acquisition, linguistic environment, behaviorist theory, language acquisition device, critical period hypothesis.

Language acquisition refers to the process through which individuals acquire a language. It is a complex and fascinating process that has been the subject of extensive research in the field of linguistics. The ability to acquire language is unique to humans and is one of the defining characteristics of our species. Language acquisition is a crucial aspect of human development, as it allows individuals to communicate with others and navigate the world around them. The use of language is essential for social interaction, education, and employment, among other things.

Language acquisition begins at birth and continues throughout childhood and adolescence. During this time, children are exposed to language through their interactions with caregivers, peers, and the environment around them. They learn to recognize and produce sounds, words, and sentences, and to use language to communicate their thoughts and feelings.

One of the main benefits of language acquisition is that it enables individuals to express their thoughts and feelings. By learning a language, individuals can communicate their ideas and emotions to others, which can help them build relationships and develop a sense of belonging.

Language acquisition also plays a critical role in cognitive development. Research has shown that language acquisition is closely linked to the development of memory, attention, and problem-solving skills. By learning a language, individuals can improve their cognitive abilities and enhance their overall intellectual functioning.

Moreover, language acquisition has significant social and cultural implications. Learning a language allows individuals to connect with people from different cultures and backgrounds, which can broaden their perspectives and promote cross-cultural understanding. It can also open up new opportunities for travel, education, and employment.

However, the process of language acquisition can be challenging, particularly for individuals who are not exposed to a rich linguistic environment from an early age. Factors such as age, exposure to language, and individual differences can all affect the ease and success of language acquisition.

To support language acquisition, it is essential to provide children with a rich linguistic environment that includes exposure to spoken and written language. This can be achieved through reading, conversation, and exposure to media such as books, television, and the internet.

There are two main theories of language acquisition: the behaviorist theory and the nativist theory. The behaviorist theory, which was popularized by B.F. Skinner in the mid-20th century, posits that language is acquired through reinforcement and conditioning. According to this theory, children learn language by imitating the speech of others and receiving positive feedback when they produce correct utterances.

The nativist theory, on the other hand, suggests that language acquisition is innate and biologically determined. This theory was championed by Noam Chomsky in the 1950s and 1960s. According to Chomsky, humans are born with an innate capacity for language, which he called the "language acquisition device." This device allows children to unconsciously acquire the rules of their native language without explicit instruction.

While there is still debate among linguists about the relative importance of these two theories, most agree that both play a role in language acquisition. Children do learn through imitation and reinforcement, but they also seem to have an innate ability to recognize and internalize the grammar of their language.

Another important aspect of language acquisition is the critical period hypothesis. This hypothesis suggests that there is a limited window of time during which children can acquire language easily and fluently. After this period, which is thought to end around puberty, language acquisition becomes more difficult and less successful.

Research has shown that this critical period is influenced by factors such as age, exposure to language, and the quality of language input. Children who are exposed to a rich linguistic environment from an early age, for example, are more likely to acquire language quickly and easily than those who are not.

In addition to these factors, there are also individual differences in language acquisition. Some children are naturally better at learning languages than others, and some may have specific language impairments or disorders that affect their ability to acquire language.

Overall, language acquisition is a complex and multifaceted process that is still not fully understood. However, ongoing research in this area continues to shed light on how children learn language and what factors influence this process. By understanding more about language

References

McLaughlin, Scott. (2010). *Verbal behavior by B.F. Skinner: Contributions to analyzing early language learning*. The journal of speech and language pathology, applied behavior analysis.

Skinner, B. F. (1968). *The technology of teaching*. New York: Meredith Corporation.

Skinner B. F. (1957). *Verbal behavior*. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts.

Chomsky, N. (1950). *Aspects of the Theory of Syntax*. Cambridge: MIT Press.